

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AND INVOLVEMENT OF PUPILS IN CO-CURRICULAR/EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES: ITS IMPACT ON THEIR PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study was to determine the implementation of and pupils' involvement in co-curricular/extracurricular activities and its impact on their academic performance at Sta. Isabel Sur Elementary School. Involved as respondents in the study were pupils and teachers from grades four to six. The descriptive survey method was employed with questionnaire as the main data-gathering tool. Results of the study show that pupils perceived strong implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities along economic, physical, and intellectual activities and citizenship training. The pupils showed moderate to average involvement in these activities. Pupils' involvement in co-curricular/extracurricular activities had an impact on their personal development as well as academic performance. Workload of teachers and principals, financial expenses and lack of school facilities were identified by respondents as problems met in the implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities. Pupils involved in co-curricular/extracurricular activities performed better academically than those who were not involved. The teachers had better perceptions on the implementation of physical, citizenship and socio-cultural activities while the pupils were on intellectual activities.

Keywords: *Co-Curricular/Extracurricular Activities, Personal Development, Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a broad concept that transcends the four walls of the classrooms. In the 21st century, the academic type of education that students are introduced to, is steadily paving the way for a whole new type of education with special focus on incorporating three major domains of education: cognitive, psychomotor and affective. This type of learning must involve more than literacy alone. In this new trend of education, the traditional 3Rs or traditional content areas become avenues for imparting a whole array of skills. These skills will allow students to function, learn and adapt throughout life in this post-modern world.

Since one of the objectives of the schools is to discover and enhance the different abilities and interests of the individual learner so as to equip him with skills for productive endeavor and thus prepare him for work in the real world and for further formal studies in higher education, co-curricular activities have always been linked to and a bridge between learning and living. These activities provide links between the curriculum and the life of students. These activities offer opportunities for students to use knowledge and skills learned in the classroom and to develop and enhance personal qualities that are difficult to teach in the classroom.

The Department of Education here in the Philippines had embraced the new curriculum of Kto12 which aims to provide sufficient time for mastery of concepts and skills and develop lifelong learners. This curriculum is more on performance based system of learning. The researcher believes that co-curricular activities are another way to help learners equip, develop and master skills that take place outside typical pen and pencil classroom experience.

The meaning of co-curricular activities revolves around its different feature and characteristics. For the overall development of a child, curriculum is not only the single criteria. The holistic growth as well as the development of the various facets of personality development of children; classroom teaching should be supplemented with co-curricular activities. These out of class activities affect all domains of life such as cognitive (intellectual), emotional, social, moral, cultural and aesthetic. Co-curricular activities are more focused upon cognitive aspect. They help in intellectual development competitiveness, excellence, quality achievements, creativeness and enthusiasm.

According to Singh (2017), the scope of co-curricular activities in school shows that co-curricular activities not only make the students active and energetic but also enable them to harness their in-depth potential. It enhances knowledge in many domains, which benefits the student as well as the school. Co-curricular activities are good platforms to secure the future both professionally and socially and promote leadership quality. It nurtures student's ability in cooperation, coordination, organization and leads them toward leadership. Extra-curricular activities provide exposure to personality and help in psychological and sociological transformation. Schools channelize the energy of students with the help of extra-curricular activities so that proper

realization of student's energy and potential can be ensued. Co-curricular activities are extremely important in the case of struggling children who are full of energy.

Co-curricular activities are also referred to as Extra-curricular activities. Grammatically, there is a difference between the two. Extra-curricular is self-explanatory activities which are extra or additional to curricular but is more leisure oriented than learning oriented. Extra-curricular activities are mostly conducted after school hours. They generally don't complement academic studies. However, some of the activities overlap one another. Some extra-curricular activities are considered co-curricular while others are extra-curricular. It helps to develop the all-round personality of the students to face the undaunted task and turbulent world of future. Experience and accolades gained through many of these activities help during internships and other school sponsored work programs.

Under the K to12 program, the grades between academic and extra-curricular activities are being separated, meaning, points from extracurricular activities and academics are no longer added unlike before. The researcher believes that this is another aspect that will greatly affect the academic performance of students since throughout her education and years of teaching experiences she has observed that participation in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities really affects the students' academic performance.

The researcher also has observed that there are two viewpoints of students as well as parents about participation in co-curricular and extracurricular activities. Some are in favor because they find these activities excellent opportunities to discover new meaningful educational experiences. Others oppose to join because they feel that involvement in such activities may draw attention away from academics.

It is for this reason, the researcher being an educator wants to look into the implementation and involvement of pupils in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities and determine its effect on their academic performance. Result of the study is deemed important basis for enhancing co-curricular and extra-curricular program at Sta. Isabel Sur Elementary School.

Research Questions

The study determined the implementation of and pupils' involvement in co-curricular/ extra-curricular activities and its impact on their personal development and academic performance.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent are Co-Curricular Activities/Extra-Curricular Activities in Sta. Isabel Sur Elementary School implemented as perceived by the pupils?
 - a. Physical Activities
 - b. Intellectual/Literary Activities
 - c. Citizenship Training
 - d. Socio-Cultural Activities

- e. Economic Activities
 - f. Aesthetic/ Cultural Activities
2. To what extent do the pupils participate or get involved in Co-curricular Activities and Extra-Curricular Activities as perceived by the pupils?
 - a. Physical Activities
 - b. Intellectual/Literary Activities
 - c. Citizenship Training
 - d. Socio-Cultural Activities
 - e. Economic Activities
 - f. Aesthetic/ Cultural Activities
 3. What is the impact of pupils' involvement in Co-curricular Activities/Extra-Curricular Activities on their personal development and academic performance?
 4. What are the problems encountered in the implementation of co-curricular/extra-curricular activities as perceived by pupils and teachers?
 5. What is the academic performance of the pupils?
 6. Is there a significant difference in the implementation of co-curricular and extra-curricular activities as perceived by the teachers and pupils?
 7. Is there any significant relationship between the implementation and involvement of pupil-respondents in co-curricular and extracurricular activities and their academic performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive method was used in this study. The focus was on the degree of implementation and involvement of students in co-curricular/extracurricular activities. The objective of this study was to understand how participation of co-curricular/ extracurricular activities can affect pupils' academic performance.

The specific type of descriptive method used in this study was descriptive survey. McCombes (2023) pointed out that a descriptive survey method is a process of learning pertinent information about an existing situation.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Sta. Isabel Sur Elementary School. The school is located at Barangay Sta. Isabel Sur, City of Ilagan, Province of Isabela, Region 02. Sta. Isabel Sur is one of the schools in the Northwest district of the City Division of Ilagan under the supervision of the Division Office of the Department of Education. The school consists of 596 total population, 19 teachers and 1 administrator/principal.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The total school population for school year 2018-19 was 596 . The population for the study comprised three (3) grade levels including three (3) sections of Grade IV, two (2) sections of Grade V and two sections of Grade VI students of Sta. Isabel Sur Elementary School . Non-probability sampling method was adopted for the selection of the sample for the present study. The sample consisted of a total 249 pupils, 90 pupils from grade four, 78 from grade five and 81 from grade six.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher acted on the following steps in the realization of the study: The researcher coordinated with the school administration and got approval for the conduct of the study through a formal letter. After the approval of the school administrator, the researcher prepared the questionnaire needed to gather data and coordinated with the teacher in-charge. After permission was obtained, the researcher identified first the pupils who were involved and not involved in any co-curricular and extracurricular activities. The researcher floated the questionnaire to the teachers and to those identified respondents involved with the assistance of the teacher in –charge. The questionnaire was the main data gathering instrument of the study which was modified and structured in such a way that respondents could answer it easily. Then the researcher also requested the academic performance of all the respondents from their class advisers. Also included were those respondents not involved in the study. The final step was the retrieval of the questionnaire. The gathered data were, tallied, tabulated, and computed using the appropriate statistical tool to analyze the findings and results of the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following are statistical tools used in the study:

1. Frequency (f) and Percentage Count (P) was used to determine the ratio of the parts (f) to the whole expresses in percent. The formula is $P = f/N \times 100\%$. Number (N) and Frequencies (f) refers to frequencies used in determining the percent computation of the academic performance of pupils who are involved and not involved in co-curricular/extracurricular activities.
2. Rank was used to determine the hierarchy or he relative importance of variables in relation to one another. In this study, Rank will was also used to determine the level of the items regarding the problems encountered in the implementation and involvement of pupils in co-curricular/extracurricular activities and the reasons that motivate them to join.

3. Weighted Mean (WM) described the general trend of reactions of the student respondents, using the formula

$$WM = \frac{\sum fw}{N}$$

Where WM = Weighted Means

fw = sum of the frequency of each respective weigh times the weight

This statistical computation was used to determine the degree of implementation and participation or involvement of pupils in co-curricular/extracurricular activities along the different areas specified in the Questionnaire.

4. The Likert Scale was used in this study to determine the degree of implementation, degree of participation or involvement in co-curricular and extracurricular activities.

Scale	Limit of Description	Degree of Implementation	Degree of Participation
5	4.20-5.00	Very Much Implemented	Very Much Involved
4	3.40-4.19	Much Implemented	Much Involved
3	2.60-3.39	Moderately Implemented	Moderately Involved
2	1.80-2.59	Fairly Implemented	Fairly Involved
1	1.00-1.79	Not Implemented	Not Involved

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. To what extent are Co-Curricular Activities/Extra-Curricular Activities in Sta. Isabel Sur Elementary School implemented as perceived by the pupils?

a. Physical Activities

Table 1
Extent of Implementation of Co-curricular/Extracurricular Activities in terms of Physical Activities

Physical Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Athletics	4.10	Much Implemented
Health and Sanitation Campaign	2.90	Moderately Implemented
Nutrition Program (cook fest, poster, slogan contest etc.)	4.47	Very Much Implemented
Mean	3.82	Much Implemented

Table 1 presents the mean and qualitative description of the degree of implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of physical activities. An overall mean of 3.82 presents a *much implemented* set of activities.

Data reveal that co-curricular/extracurricular activities implemented in terms of nutrition programs were *very much implemented* with a mean value of 4.47. This is followed by the mean value of 4.10 for athletics which was *much implemented* while health and sanitation campaign was *implemented* with only a mean value of 2.90 described as *moderately implemented*. This implies that health and sanitation campaign as well as athletics should be given equal importance for implementation since they directly affect the pupils' well-being. Extracurricular activities, particularly those related to physical health, such as athletics, nutrition programs, and health campaigns, are essential for promoting holistic student development. According to Fredricks and Eccles (2006), participation in extracurricular activities can lead to positive outcomes in students' physical health, social development, and academic performance. Schools that provide structured and consistent physical activities, including nutrition programs, are more likely to see improvements in students' overall well-being and academic achievements. However, inconsistencies in the implementation of these activities, as seen with the moderate implementation of health and sanitation campaigns, may limit the potential benefits. Studies suggest that inadequate implementation of health-related programs may stem from a lack of resources, support, or awareness (Durlak et al., 2010). Therefore, increasing efforts toward health education and sanitation campaigns in schools is necessary to ensure that students receive comprehensive physical education.

B. Intellectual/Literary Activities

Table 2
Extent of Implementation of Co-curricular/Extracurricular Activities in terms of Intellectual/Literary Activities

Intellectual/Literary Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
English Club (Essay Writing, Reading/Storytelling)	3.96	Much Implemented
Filipino Club	4.24	Very Much Implemented
Math Club	4.09	Much Implemented
Science Club	3.95	Much Implemented
A.P. Club	3.94	Much Implemented
E.P.P. Club	3.94	Much Implemented
School Publication/ Campus Journalism	4.09	Much Implemented
MEAN	3.66	Much Implemented

It is shown by the data that Co-curricular/Extracurricular Activities in terms of Intellectual/Literary Activities in Filipino Club were *very much implemented* with a mean value of 4.24. All the other activities were *much implemented* like those sponsored by the English Club, Math Club, Science Club, A.P. Club, EPP Club and the School Publication/ Campus Journalism. It appears that both teachers and pupils have preference for co-curricular and extra-curricular activities of the Filipino club. One probable reason is their familiarity and ease with the language used in the activities. Extracurricular and co-curricular activities are crucial in fostering student engagement, enhancing learning experiences, and contributing to the overall development of students. Studies have shown that these activities positively impact both academic and social outcomes (Eccles & Barber, 1999). Specifically, co-curricular activities, such as clubs and organizations, allow students to apply knowledge from the classroom to real-world settings, reinforcing skills like leadership, teamwork, and communication (Fredricks & Eccles, 2006). In the context of language clubs, like the Filipino Club, there is a distinct advantage for students and teachers who share a common linguistic background.

The familiarity and comfort with the Filipino language, as highlighted in the data, likely contribute to the strong preference for activities conducted in this language. Studies by Roxas and Gabriel (2016) have shown that the use of the native language in extracurricular activities can enhance participation and engagement, as students feel more confident expressing themselves. Additionally, teachers who facilitate these activities may find it easier to connect with students, leading to more meaningful interactions and learning experiences. The strong implementation of activities in the Filipino Club, as indicated by the mean value of 4.24, underscores the significance of language in the effectiveness of co-curricular activities. In contrast, activities sponsored by clubs that use English or specialized subjects may face more challenges in engagement due to the language barrier or complexity of subject matter (Bernardo, 2000). This suggests that while other clubs are "much implemented," the Filipino Club's activities stand out because they tap into students' comfort zones, thus maximizing their participation and learning.

C. Citizenship Training

Table 3
Extent of Implementation of Co-curricular/Extracurricular Activities
in terms of Citizenship Training

Citizenship Training	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
a. Boy Scouting	4.58	Very Much Implemented
b. Girl Scouting	4.58	Very Much Implemented
c. Supreme Pupil Government	4.30	Very Much Implemented
d. Community and Civic Programs Participation	2.80	Moderately Implemented

MEAN	4.07	Much Implemented
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Table 3 reveals that co-curricular/ extracurricular activities in terms of citizenship training were *much implemented* with an overall mean value of 4.07. Among these activities, Boy Scouting, Girl Scouting and Supreme Pupil Government were activities that were *very much implemented* while community and civic program participation was *moderately implemented* with a mean value of 2.80.

It can be deduced from the data that in terms of Citizenship Training, the school has limited relationship with the community. Its participation in activities initiated by the community is not active considering the fact that there should be strong relationship between school and the community. Extracurricular and co-curricular activities play a significant role in enhancing students' citizenship education, particularly through programs such as Boy Scouting, Girl Scouting, and school government organizations. According to Kraft (1998), these activities not only develop leadership skills and a sense of responsibility but also foster civic engagement, which is crucial for building stronger school-community relationships. Moreover, Harris and Wilkes (2013) argue that when schools actively participate in community-driven activities, such as civic programs and local events, students are provided with real-world contexts to apply their learning, which deepens their understanding of citizenship roles.

D. Socio-Cultural Activities

Table 4

Extent of Implementation of Co-curricular/Extracurricular Activities
in terms of Socio-Cultural Activities

Socio-Cultural Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
a. Celebration of Fiestas	4.50	Very Much Implemented
b. Socio-Cultural Shows	2.20	Fairly Implemented
c. Dance Competitions	2.14	Fairly Implemented
d. Drama Competitions	1.47	Not Implemented
e. Mini School Cultural Museum	1.22	Not Implemented
MEAN	2.30	Fairly Implemented

Table 4 shows that socio-cultural activities under co-curricular/extracurricular activities were *fairly implemented* as seen in the mean value of 2.30. However, Celebration of Fiestas was a *very much implemented* activity with a mean value of 4.50. It is revealed that Socio-cultural shows and Dance Competitions were just *fairly implemented* activities. Meanwhile, the activities that were *not implemented* at all include Drama Competitions and creation of Mini School Cultural Museum. Generally, the implementation of socio-cultural activities leaves much to be desired, that is, the degree of implementation is just average.

E. Economic Activities

Table 5

Extent of Implementation of Co-curricular/Extracurricular Activities
in terms of Economic Activities

Economic Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
a. School Vegetable Gardening (Gulayan sa Paaralan)	4.82	Very Much Implemented
b. Tree Planting	4.01	Much Implemented
c. School Flower/ Potted Plant Gardening	4.38	Very Much Implemented
d. YES-O Club	4.34	Very Much Implemented
MEAN	4.39	Very Much Implemented

Table 5 indicates that co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of economic activities were *very much implemented* as shown by the overall mean value of 4.39. This means the activities were very much implemented with school vegetable gardening (*Gulayan sa Paaralan*) having the highest mean value of 4.82 except for Tree Planting (much implemented). Overall, this area exhibits a satisfactory implementation of activities. For instance, Buhat and Ruiz (2019) discussed the implementation of the "Gulayan sa Paaralan" (School Vegetable Gardening) program in various public schools in the Philippines. They found that the program significantly contributes to both the nutritional intake of students and their practical knowledge of agriculture, with high levels of implementation and satisfaction among participants. Moreover, they noted that hands-on gardening activities help students connect theoretical lessons with real-world applications, particularly in economics and environmental sciences. In a similar vein, Santos and Perez (2020) explored the impact of tree planting initiatives in schools as part of environmental education. Their findings showed that while tree planting is generally well-received, its implementation is often hindered by logistical challenges such as the availability of saplings and proper maintenance practices. Despite these issues, they concluded that the activity fosters a sense of environmental responsibility among students, with a majority indicating that they felt more connected to nature after participating in such programs.

F. Aesthetic/ Cultural Activities

Table 6

Extent of Implementation of Co-curricular/Extracurricular Activities
in terms of Aesthetics/ Cultural Activities

Aesthetics/ Cultural Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
a. Drum and Bugle Corps Participation	1.34	Not Implemented
b. Pupils' Choir (school/church/community)	1.35	Not Implemented
c. Dance Troupe Creation	1.76	Not Implemented
d. Painting/Illustrations/ Drawing	3.51	Moderately Implemented
MEAN	2.00	Fairly Implemented

Table 6 presents the degree of implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of aesthetic/ cultural activities with a mean value of 2.00 described as a *fairly implemented*. The data reveals that Painting/ Illustrations/ Drawing activity was *moderately implemented* with a mean value of 3.51. Other activities such as Drum and Bugle Corps Participation, Pupil's Choir and Dance Troupe Creation were *not implemented* at all. In the context of aesthetic and cultural activities, extracurricular programs play a vital role in fostering students' creativity and cultural awareness. According to Darling, Caldwell, and Smith (2005), extracurricular involvement, particularly in arts and cultural activities, contributes to a more holistic education, providing students with opportunities to express themselves, collaborate with peers, and develop skills that are not typically emphasized in the academic curriculum. However, the implementation of such programs varies widely depending on school resources and administrative priorities. The study further points out that schools often struggle to balance extracurricular offerings, with some activities, like music and arts, receiving less emphasis due to logistical challenges, limited funding, and a lack of trained personnel.

In conclusion, among co-curricular/ extracurricular activities implemented in Sta. Isabel Sur Elementary School, certain economic activities are perceived to be *very much implemented* while socio-cultural and aesthetic/cultural activities are only observed as *fairly implemented*.

2. To what extent do the pupils participate or get involved in Co-curricular Activities and Extra-Curricular Activities as perceived by the pupils?

a. Physical Activities

Table 7

Extent of Pupils' Participation/Involvement in Co-Curricular/Extracurricular Activities in terms of Physical Activities as Perceived by the Pupils

Physical Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
a. Athletics	2.25	Fairly Involved
b. Health and Sanitation Campaign	2.27	Fairly Involved
c. Nutrition Program (cookfest, poster,slogan contest etc.)	3.26	Moderately Involved
MEAN	2.59	Fairly Involved

Table 7 shows the pupils' degree of participation/involvement in co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of physical activities as perceived by them. As revealed by the data, in terms of physical activities, the pupils' degree of participation/involvement was *fairly involved* with a mean value of 2.59. Pupils *moderately involved* or participated in nutrition program activities (3.26), *fairly involved* in Athletics (2.25) and Health and Sanitation Campaign (2.27). The data imply that pupils of Sta. Isabel Elementary School have limited involvement in physical activities. The involvement of students in physical activities, particularly through co-curricular and extracurricular programs, is a significant contributor to their overall physical and mental development. According to Cheon et al. (2019), active participation in physical education and sports programs enhances students' physical fitness, motor skills, and overall health, promoting a balanced lifestyle that extends beyond the classroom. Furthermore, the research highlights that schools offering a variety of physical activities, such as sports, health programs, and nutrition education, tend to encourage higher levels of participation among students. However, the degree of involvement can vary due to factors such as access to resources, student interest, and the school's emphasis on physical development. In the case of Sta. Isabel Elementary School, where students show only moderate participation in nutrition programs and limited involvement in athletics and health campaigns, this mirrors findings from other studies showing that without adequate support and emphasis, students' engagement in physical activities can remain low (Cooper et al., 2018). Schools that foster an environment conducive to active participation, including offering well-structured physical activities, providing role models, and ensuring sufficient time for physical education, typically see higher student engagement (Fredricks & Eccles, 2006).

b. Intellectual/ Literary Activities

Table 8

Extent of Pupils' Participation/Involvement in Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities in terms of Intellectual/Literary Activities as Perceived by the Pupils

Intellectual/Literary Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
English Club Activities	1.46	Not Involved
Filipino Club Activities	1.88	Fairly Involved
Math Club Activities	1.46	Not Involved
Science Club Activities	1.39	Not Involved
A.P. Club Activities	1.43	Not Involved
E.P.P. Club Activities	1.56	Not Involved
MEAN	1.47	Not Involved

The table above shows that pupils generally perceived no participation or involvement in intellectual/ literary activities with the mean of 1.47. Pupils *fairly* got *involved* or participated in Filipino club with a mean value of 1.88 while they did *not* get *involved* nor participate in all other activities. While Table 1-B shows implementation by the school of intellectual/Literary Activities, the pupils do not seem to have any involvement except for activities of the Filipino Club. Table 1-B reflects that activities in the Filipino Club were very much implemented.

c. Citizenship Training

Table 9

Extent of Pupils' Participation/Involvement in Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities in terms of Citizenship Training as Perceived by the Pupils

Citizenship Training	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Boy Scouting	3.09	Moderately Involved
Girl Scouting	3.14	Moderately Involved
Supreme Pupil Government	1.41	Not Involved
Community Programs Participation	1.56	Not Involved
MEAN	2.23	Fairly Involved

Table 9 shows the degree of pupils' participation in co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of Citizenship Training in which they perceived themselves to be *fairly involved* with an overall mean value of 2.23. Both Boy Scouting and Girl Scouting were *moderately participated* in by the pupils while Supreme Pupil Government and the Community Programs Participation were activities they did not participate in at all. It is surprising to note that pupil-respondents perceived no involvement in the SPG and Community Programs while data from Table 1-C indicated that such activities were shown to be *very much/ moderately implemented*.

d. Socio-Cultural Activities

Table 10

Extent of Pupils' Participation/Involvement in Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities in terms of Socio-Cultural Activities as Perceived by the Pupils

Socio-Cultural Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Celebration of Fiestas	3.04	Moderately Involved
Socio-Cultural Shows	1.34	Not Involved
Dance Competitions	1.36	Not Involved
Drama Competitions	1.10	Not Involved
Mini School Cultural Museum	1.03	Not Involved
MEAN	1.57	Not Involved

Table 10 shows that the pupils perceived no involvement in co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of socio-cultural activities with overall mean value of 1.57. Celebration of Fiestas was where pupils got *moderately involved* with a mean value of 3.04. Other activities such as Socio-cultural Shows, Dance and Drama Competitions and Mini School Cultural Museum were shown to be not participated in at all by the pupil-respondents. Since fiesta celebration has been deeply ingrained into the Filipino culture, it is no surprise that the pupils have involvement in this activity.

e. Economic Activities

Table 11

Extent of Pupils' Participation/Involvement in Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities in terms of Economic Activities as Perceived by the Pupils

Economic Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
School Vegetable Gardening (<i>Gulayan sa Paaralan</i>)	4.52	Very Much Involved
Tree Planting	3.32	Moderately Involved
School Flower/ Potted Plant Gardening	3.60	Moderately Involved
YES-O Club	1.62	Not Involved
MEAN	3.27	Moderately Involved

Table 11 shows that the pupil-respondents were *moderately involved* in co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of economic activities with an overall mean value of 3.27. The pupils were *very much involved* in School Vegetable Gardening (*Gulayan sa Paaralan*) with a mean value of 4.52 and were *moderately involved* in Tree Planting and School Flower/Potted Plant Gardening. However, they were *not involved* in YES-O Club. This set of activities obtained the highest mean value (3.27). Similarly, Table 1-e had the highest mean at 4.39. The data imply that the pupils give importance to

planting of vegetables, trees and flowering plants as income generating (economic) activities.

f. Aesthetic/Cultural Activities

Table 12

Extent of Pupils’ Participation/Involvement in Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities in terms of Aesthetics/Cultural Activities as Perceived by the Pupils

Aesthetics/ Cultural Activities	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
a. Drum and Bugle Corps Participation	1.12	Not Involved
b. Pupils' Choir (school/church/community)	1.27	Not Involved
c. Dance Troupe Creation	1.16	Not Involved
d. Painting/Illustrations/ Drawing	1.11	Not Involved
MEAN	1.17	Not Involved

Table 12 shows the pupils’ co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of Aesthetics/cultural activities where they had no involvement as shown by the mean value of 1.17. This data in a way agrees with the information found in Table 1- F. It is implied by the data that pupils do not have interest in joining any of the aesthetics/cultural activities in the school.

Overall results indicate that there are activities in which the pupils perceive zero involvement or no participation such as Intellectual, Socio-cultural and Aesthetic/cultural activities. Economic activities are activities where they have moderate or average participation.

3. What is the impact of pupils’ involvement in Co-curricular Activities/Extra-Curricular Activities on their personal development and academic performance?

Table 13

Impact of Pupils’ Involvement in Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities on their Personal Development as Perceived by the Pupils

Impact of Joining the Activities	Frequency	Rank
1. Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities has helped me identify my strengths and weaknesses.	184	1
2. Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have developed my talents and abilities.	182	2
3. Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have brought out my inborn talents and skills.	181	4
4. Joining Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities can promote friendship /camaraderie/ social skill	181	4

5. Joining Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have developed my self- confidence and self-esteem.	181	4
6. Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have prepared me how to become a good citizen.	180	6
7. Joining Co-Curricular/Extracurricular activities can promote good/sound mental and physical health.	177	7.5
8. Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have encouraged me how to utilize my free/ leisure time	177	7.5
9. Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities served as my training for leadership.	175	9
10.Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have enhanced my educational experiences.	171	10
11.Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have exposed me to a wider environment outside the school.	168	11
12.Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have directed my energies towards productive performance in school.	166	12
13. There are rewards and recognition given in joining the Co-curricular/extra-curricular activities.	162	13
14.Others (specify)	39	14

Table 13 shows the frequency and rank of statements pertaining to the impact of pupils' involvement in co-curricular/extra-curricular activities on their personal development and academic performance based on their perception.

Data reveal that the pupils foremost found co-curricular/extra-curricular activities to have helped them identify their strengths and weaknesses (Rank 1). They also found co-curricular and extra-curricular activities affecting the development of their talents and abilities (Rank 2). Likewise, they perceived that these activities have brought out their inborn talents and skills promoted friendship, camaraderie and social skill and developed their self-confidence and self-esteem (Rank 4). That co-curricular/extra-curricular activities have prepared them to become good citizen was ranked 6 by them.

Both at 7.5 place were co-curricular/extra-curricular activities having promoted the pupils good/sound mental and physical health and have encouraged them to utilize their free and leisure time. Pupils ranked at number 9 the impact of their involvement in CCA/ECA on their leadership training. Moreover, the pupils have found the activities to have enhanced their educational experiences (Rank 10), exposed them to a wider environment outside the school (Rank 11), directed their energies towards productive school performance (Rank 12) and received rewards and recognition for joining the co-curricular/extra-curricular activities. Other impacts were last (Rank 14).

These data suggest that the pupils have intrinsic motivation in joining co-curricular/extra-curricular activities as shown by their perception of what greatly impacted them.

4. What are the problems encountered in the implementation of co-curricular/extra-curricular activities as perceived by pupils and teachers?

Table 14

Problems Met in the Implementation of Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities as Perceived by Pupil-Respondents

Problems Encountered	Frequency	Rank
Too many school works of teachers and principals.	111	1
Too many expenses involved.	105	2
Parents do not cooperate.	79	3
Lack of facilities for the programs	57	4
Goals/Objectives are not clear.	55	5
Little information about the programs.	54	6
There are difficult activities that may be harmful.	47	7
Too many activities	45	8
Teachers and students are not involved in planning	28	9
Lack of fund / financial support from the administrators	24	10
Negative attitude of the teachers	22	11
Other organizations do not cooperate.	17	12
Pupil's safety not assured.	13	13.5
There are no rewards/incentives from participating in the program.	13	13.5
Community people do not cooperate.	12	15.5
Negative attitude of the administrators	12	15.5
Teachers do not have enough training and orientation about the program	11	17

The table above provides data on the problems encountered in the implementation of extra and co-curricular activities as perceived by the pupils. These problems were ranked.

As revealed in the table, the pupils considered “too many school works of teachers and principals” the foremost impediment to the implementation of co-curricular and extra-curricular activities at school with a frequency of 111. It was followed by “too many expenses involved” with a frequency of 105 and “parents do not cooperate” (79). Ranking fourth was “lack of facilities for the programs” and fifth was “goals/objectives of the

program are not clear” with frequencies of 57 and 55 respectively. With a frequency of 54, “little information about the programs” was ranked 6th problem by the pupils followed by “there are difficult activities that may be harmful” (7th) and “too many activities” (8th) with frequencies of 47 and 45 respectively.

Also problems seen by the pupils were that “teachers and students are not involved in planning” (9th), “lack of fund / financial support from the administrators” (10th), “negative attitude of the teachers (11th) and “other organizations do not cooperate (12th). The pupil’s no assurance for safety and no rewards/incentives from participating in the program were both at 13th place. Also tie for 15th place were problems that “community people do not cooperate” and administrators had “negative attitude.” The least problem considered by the pupils was that the teachers did not have enough training and orientation about the program.

Table 15

Problems Met in the Implementation of Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities as Perceived by Teacher-Respondents

Problems Encountered	Frequency	Rank
Too many school works of teachers and principals.	18	1
Too many expenses involved.	15	2
Too many activities	14	3
Lack of facilities for the programs	13	4
Lack of fund / financial support from the administrators	12	5
Teachers do not have enough training and orientation about the program	12	5
Parents do not cooperate.	8	6
Teachers and students are not involved in planning	7	7
Pupil’s safety not assured.	6	8
Negative attitude of the teachers	5	9
Little information about the programs.	5	9
Negative attitude of the administrators	4	10
Other organizations do not cooperate.	4	10
There are difficult activities that may be harmful.	2	11
There are no rewards/incentives from participating in the program.	1	12
Community people do not cooperate.	1	12
Goals/Objectives are not clear.	1	12

The table above shows the teachers’ perception of the problems that got in the way of implementing co-curricular and extra-curricular activities in school. With the highest frequency of 18, “too many school works of teachers and principals” was the foremost problem. This is followed by “too many expenses involved” with a frequency of 15. The third problem as ranked by the teachers was there were “too many activities”

with a frequency of 14. “Lack of facilities for the programs” was the fourth most encountered program as perceived by the teachers. “Lack of fund / financial support from the administrators” and “teachers do not have enough training and orientation about the program” were problems both in fifth place.

Parents not cooperating in implementing the activities was the 6th problem identified by the teacher-respondents. It is followed by teachers and students “not being involved in planning” (7th) and the “pupil’s safety not being assured” (8th). Tie for 9th place were problems “negative attitude of the teachers” and “little information about the programs”. The negative attitude of the administrators and non-cooperation of other organizations were problems at 10th place while the presence of difficult activities that may be harmful was ranked 11th by the respondents. Finally, the teachers found “community people not cooperative and the goals/objectives of the activities not clear” the least problems, both at 12th place.

Comparing the perceptions of student and teachers on the problems encountered in the implementation of co-curricular/extra-curricular activities, the researcher found that both groups agreed that the workload of teachers and principals was the foremost problem. This problem makes it difficult to effectively carry out the co-curricular/extra-curricular activities. Teachers and principals’ time is very limited because they have many things to attend to. Both groups of respondents were also shown to agree that the conduct of co-curricular/extra-curricular activities involve too many expenses, putting this problem at second place. Activities on co-curricular/extra-curricular need sufficient funding for successful implementation and such require substantial amount which is charged against school fund.

Still another problem where both groups seem to have agreed is the lack of school facilities (4th place). Teachers and pupils see that there are not enough facilities in school to conduct co-curricular/extra-curricular activities. Other problems were variedly ranked by the respondents based on their personal/individual assessment or perceptions.

5. What is the academic performance of the pupils?

Table 16

Academic Performance of Involved and Not Involved Pupils in Co-Curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities

Grading Scale	Qualitative Description	Involved		Not Involved	
		F	%	F	%
90-100	Outstanding	27	14.5	0	0
85-89	Very Satisfactory	89	47.8	6	9.5
80-84	Satisfactory	70	37.6	56	88.8

75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0	0	0
Below 75	Did not Meet Expectation	0	0	1	1.6
	TOTAL	186	100	63	100

Table 16 reflects the frequency and percentage distribution of the academic performance of involved and not involved pupils.

As shown by the data, 186 pupils were involved in co-curricular/extra-curricular activities and 63 were not. Of those involved, 27 (14.5 %) had *outstanding* academic performance while there was none among those who were not involved. 89 (47.8%) of those involved got *very satisfactory* academic performance while six got the same rating from those not involved. There were seventy (70) or 37.6% pupils involved who received *satisfactory* rating and fifty-six (56) or 88.8 % of those not involved got the same rating. No one from either group had *fairly satisfactory* rating. From those involved pupils, there was no one who *did not meet expectation* while there was one from those not involved.

The bulk of respondents from those who had involvement in co-curricular/extra-curricular activities achieved *very satisfactory* and *satisfactory* academic performances. On the part of those who did not get involved, majority had *satisfactory* academic performance. These data imply that the pupils show average academic performance.

6. Is there a significant difference in the implementation of co-curricular and extra-curricular activities as perceived by the teachers and pupils?

Table 17

Results of Significant Difference in the Implementation of the Co-Curricular and Extra-Curricular Activities as Perceived by the Teachers and Pupils

Teachers' and Pupils' Perception in the Implementation of Co-curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities	Mean		Computed value of <i>t</i>	Tabular value of <i>t</i>	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	Teachers	Pupils					
Physical Activities	4.07	3.81	2.00	1.96	$t_c > t_t$	Reject H_0	Significant
Intellectual Activities	3.15	3.59	2.20	1.96	$t_c > t_t$	Reject H_0	Significant
Citizenship Training	4.56	4.03	2.65	1.96	$t_c > t_t$	Reject H_0	Significant

Socio-Cultural Activities	2.63	2.09	3.38	1.96	$t_c > t_t$	Reject Ho	Significant
Economic and Aesthetic/Cultural Activities	4.11	4.26	1.00	1.96	$t_c < t_t$	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 17 presents the results of significant difference in the implementation of the, co-curricular and extra-curricular activities as perceived by the teachers and pupils.

The results show that the computed t-values are greater than the t-tabular value except for economic and aesthetic/cultural activities. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the implementation of the co-curricular and extra-curricular activities as perceived by the teachers and pupils. It implies that the teachers' perceptions in the implementation of physical, intellectual, citizenship training and socio-cultural activities differ from that of the pupils. It is further inferred as indicated by the means in the table above that the teachers have better perceptions on the implementation of physical, citizenship and socio-cultural activities while the pupils are on intellectual activities.

However, there is no significant difference in the implementation of economic and aesthetic/cultural activities as perceived by the teachers and pupils as evidenced by the t-computed value which is less than the t-tabular value. It suggests that the teachers and pupils do not differ in their perceptions of the implementation of the said activities. Thus, the two groups of respondents have similar perceptions in the implementation of such activities.

7. Is there any significant relationship between the implementation and involvement of pupil-respondents in co-curricular and extracurricular activities and their academic performance?

A. Implementation

Table 18

Results of Significant Relationship between the Implementation of Co-Curricular/extracurricular Activities and the Academic Performance of Pupils

Variables	Computed Value of r	Tabular value of r	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Physical Activities and Academic Performance	0.1769	0.0505	$r_c > r_t$	Reject Ho	Significant
Intellectual/Literary Activities and		0.0505	$r_c > r_t$	Reject Ho	Significant

Academic Performance	0.1386				
Citizenship Training and Academic Performance	0.1404	0.0505	$r_c > r_t$	Reject Ho	Significant
Socio-Cultural Activities and Academic Performance	- 0.1540	- 0.0505	$r_c > r_t$	Reject Ho	Significant
Economic and Aesthetic/Cultural Activities and Academic Performance	0.0281	0.0505	$r_c < r_t$	Accept Ho	Not Significant

The results of significant relationship between the implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities and the academic performance of the pupils are presented in Table 18.

It is revealed from the results that the r-computed values are beyond the r-tabular value except for economic activities and aesthetic/cultural activities. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is significant relationship between the implementation of the co-curricular/extracurricular activities and the academic performance of the pupils. It suggests that the pupils' academic performance is strongly affected by the implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of physical, intellectual/literary, citizenship training, and socio-cultural activities.

However, there is no significant relationship between the implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of economic and aesthetic/cultural activities and the academic performance of the pupils. It implies that the said activities have no effect on the pupils' academic performance.

B. Involvement

Table 19

Results of Significant Relationship between the Involvement of Pupils in Co-curricular/Extracurricular Activities and Their Academic Performance

Variables	Computed Value of r	Tabular value of r	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Physical Activities and Academic Performance	- 0.0392	-0.0505	rc is to the right of rt	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Intellectual/Literary Activities and Academic Performance	0.2886	0.0505	rc > rt	Reject Ho	Significant
Citizenship Training and Academic Performance	0.2970	0.0505	rc > rt	Reject Ho	Significant
Socio-Cultural Activities and Academic Performance	0.1649	0.0505	rc > rt	Reject Ho	Significant
Economic and Aesthetic/Cultural Activities and Academic Performance	0.2845	0.0505	rc > rt	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 19 displays the results of significant relationship between the involvement of pupils in the co-curricular/extracurricular activities and their academic performance.

It is evident from the results that the r-computed values are greater than the r-tabular value except for physical activities. For this reason, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis at five per cent level of significance. As a result, significant relationship exists between the involvement of the pupils in co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of intellectual/ literary, citizenship training, socio-cultural and economic and aesthetic/cultural activities, and their academic performance. It means that the pupils' involvement in intellectual, citizenship training, socio-cultural, and economic and aesthetic activities greatly affect their academic performance.

However, there is no significant relationship between the pupils' involvement in physical activities and their academic performance. It means that the pupils' academic

performance does not depend on their involvement in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities in terms of physical activities.

That pupils' involvement in co-curricular/extracurricular activities has relationship with their academic performance corroborates with the findings of Fujita (2011) stating that students who participate in extra-curricular activities benefit academically. Such effect depends on the specific activities in which the students are involved.

Conclusions

In view of the findings of the study, the following conclusion is drawn:

1. As perceived by pupils, implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities is very strong along economic activities, followed by physical activities, intellectual activities, and citizenship training. Implementation of socio-cultural activities is only average.
2. Pupils have moderate to average involvement in co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of economic activities, physical activities, and citizenship training. They do not take part in intellectual/literary activities, aesthetic/cultural activities, and socio-cultural activities except for fiesta celebration.
3. Pupils' involvement in co-curricular/extracurricular activities have an impact on their personal and academic performance as they can identify their strengths and weaknesses, develop their talents and abilities, bring out their hidden talents and skills, promote friendship, social skills, develop self-confidence and self-esteem.
4. Workload of teachers and principals, financial expenses and lack of school facilities are identified by teachers and pupils as problems encountered in the implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities.
5. Pupils involved in co-curricular/extracurricular activities excel in academic performance while those not involved turn just an average academic performance.
6. The teachers have better perceptions on the implementation of physical, citizenship and socio-cultural activities while the pupils are on intellectual activities. Meanwhile, they have similar perception on the implementation of economic and aesthetic/cultural activities.
7. The pupils' academic performance is strongly affected by the implementation of co-curricular/extracurricular activities in terms of physical, intellectual/literary, citizenship training, and socio-cultural activities. Economic and aesthetic/cultural activities do not influence the pupils' academic performance.
8. Pupils' involvement in intellectual, citizenship training, socio-cultural, and economic and aesthetic activities greatly affects their academic performance. However, their involvement in physical activities does not influence their academic performance.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. Implementation of co-curricular/extra-curricular activities in terms of economic, physical, and intellectual activities and citizenship training should be maintained.

Since implementation of socio-cultural activities was found only average, such should be made stronger by teachers and school heads.

2. Pupils' involvement in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities should be increased more particularly along intellectual/literary activities, aesthetic/cultural activities, and socio-cultural activities where they were found to have from little to no participation.
3. Because co-curricular and extracurricular activities were found to have relationship with and impact on pupils' academic performance and personal development, teachers and principals should encourage the pupils to get more actively involved in co-curricular/extracurricular activities.
4. Principals and teachers are encouraged to sit down and discuss ways on how they could revise their workload to provide ample time to implementing co-curricular/extracurricular activities. Also, they should find means like planning and budgeting to economically conduct co-curricular/extracurricular activities and address dearth of facilities.
5. Similar studies should be conducted in other areas to establish the effect of co-curricular/extracurricular activities on the academic performance and personal development of learners.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure the observance of ethical standards, the proponent wrote a letter asking permission from the principal to conduct a classroom-based action research. She likewise sought an endorsement letter from the schools' city division superintendent for the conduct of her study. All participants in the study were requested to give their consent to partake in the study.

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